

Zotero to Elexifinder: Collection, curation, and migration of bibliographical data

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Overview

- Introduction
 - Motivation
 - Previous work
- LexBib Zotero group and LexBib Wikibase
 - Bibliographical data: import, curation, migration
 - Entity disambiguation
 - Full text processing
 - LexVoc vocabulary of lexicographic terms
- Elexifinder version 2
- Outlook

Introduction

- LexBib: a small-scale digital library for Lexicography and Dictionary Research
- Why LexBib?
 - Only about 50% of 7.300 LexBib bibliographical items have DOI
 - Articles without DOI usually not indexed on the big bibliodata platforms
 - Information retrieval from cross-domain digital libraries: shortcomings
 - Search results mixed up with publications from other domains
 - Content-describing article indexation out of scope
 - Author disambiguation incomplete and inaccurate
 - Publication metadata incomplete

Introduction

- LexBib: a small-scale digital library for Lexicography and Dictionary Research
- Goals:
 - Complete covering of the discipline
 - Content-describing indexation of items by full text (or abstract text) mining, using a fine-grained controlled vocabulary of lexicographic terms
 - Validated publication metadata for citation purposes
 - Feeding Elexifinder, a discovery portal for lexicographic literature

Introduction: Previous work

- Elexifinder version 1, introduced in Kosem & Krek (2019)
- LexBib, introduced by Lindemann, Kliche & Heid (2018)
- Overlapping interests: Bibliodata meeting at eLex Sintra

LexBib bibliographical data

- Zotero
 - Recording of publication metadata, and full texts
 - In tabular or structured format, from existing bibliographies
 - Using Zotero web scraping tool: From web-repositories
 - Manual validation of metadata records (team uses „Zotero groups“)
 - Always with full text

LexBib Zotero Group

LexBib Zotero group:
<http://lexbib.org/zotero>

- Browse by collection, search for publication metadata
- Metadata download in structured formats (bibtex, etc.)
- Useful for import to own citation manager

Wikibase as LOD database solution

- Wikibase
 - Instant publishing: entity data wiki pages
 - Edit history, reversible edits
 - Discussion pages
 - User and user rights management
 - Straightforward alignment with Wikidata
 - Related tools (originally developed for Wikidata)
 - SPARQL interface & endpoint, Mediawiki API, entity data dumps
- „Wikibase as a Service“ (<http://wbstack.com>)
 - Provided to the community since 2019 by Rhizome, A. Shoreland, WMDE
 - See also: <http://wikiba.se> ; <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikibase>

LexBib bibliographical data

- Export from Zotero to LexBib Wikibase
- Mapping literals to ontology items:
 - Creators (authors, editors)
 - Containers (journal issues, etc.)
 - Events (conferences, workshops)
 - Languages (publication language)
- Export from Wikibase to Elexifinder discovery portal
 - Disambiguated entities
 - Full text body (GROBID, manual cleaning)
- Full Texts: upload to SketchEngine
 - Custom subcorpora (by event, time, etc.)

Entity disambiguation: Authors

- Open Refine
 - Initial dataset (Klaes 2021)
 - 18,000 creator statements in Zotero
 - 5,000 different names
 - 4,000 different persons
 - Updates since Aug. 2021
 - Reconciliation of Zotero name literals against LexBib Wikibase

120 matching rows (425 total)
 Show as: rows records Show: 5 10 25 50 rows

	bibItem	statement_id	coll	creator
236.	http://data.lexbib.org/entity/Q22805	Q22805-43E59BC9-D28F-4CCF-8A80-3E86B6F64DA7	26	B. T. S. Atkins
237.	http://data.le			Anna Wierzb
238.	http://data.le			Jurij D. Apre
239.	http://data.le			Sue Atkins
240.	http://data.le			Sidney I. Lan
241.	http://data.le			

Search for match

Search for "B. T. S. Atkins"

Match other cells with same content
 Match this cell only

Select an item from the list:

- Sue Atkins Q20324
a Person

Match New Item Don't Reconcile Cell Cancel

LexVoc Vocabulary of Lexicographic Terms

- SKOS vocabulary: Tree structure with “Lexicography” as root
- Description: <https://lexbib.elex.is/wiki/LexVoc>

LexVoc: Structure

- Root “Lexicography”
- Main branches
 - Dictionary Structure
 - Dictionary Type
 - Dictionary Making
 - Dictionary Use
 - Dictionary Function
 - Dictionary Distribution Type
 - Linguistic Property
 - NLP / Corpus Linguistics

LexVoc: Translation

LexVoc_dan_Danish Edit Configure Download Upload david.lindemann@ehu.eus

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starts like this

- Intransitive Verb
- Irrealis Mood
- language production**
- language reception
- layout
- learners' dictionary
- lemma
- lemma list
- lemma selection
- lemmatization

language production
Found in 135 articles

Alternatives:
 Broader term: communicative function
 Narrower term: text production
 Close match:
 Related:
 Definition: process by which people translate thoughts into spoken, written or signed words
 Babelnet ID: bn:03861954n

Language	Preferred	Alternative	Status
Danish	sprog produktion		AUTOMATIC

- 39 languages (Elexis languages)
- Call for collaboration
- Drafted translations from BabelNet, Wikidata
- Translation editing process: Lexonomy app at Elexis
- 38 bilingual dictionaries, see https://lexbib.elex.is/wiki/LexVoc_Lexonomy

Elexifinder Interface

The screenshot shows the Elexifinder web interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'B. T. Sue Atkins AND Bilingual' and a 'SEARCH' button. Below the search bar, there are filter options: 'Filter by: Locations Sources Categories Time of interest Any language'. The main content area displays 'List of publications (13 results found)'. On the left side, there is a navigation menu with options: 'List of publications', 'Top Concepts', 'Languages', 'Tag Cloud', 'Timeline', 'First Author Locations', 'Sources', 'Publication authors', and 'Concept Graph'. The main content area shows two publication entries. The first entry is 'Lexicographic Profiling: an Aid to Consistency in Dictionary Entry Design' from EURALEX (2006), dated Sun, 01 Jan 2006, by B. T. Sue Atkins et al. The second entry is 'The Contribution of Framenet to Practical Lexicography' from IJL 16/3 (2003), dated Mon, 01 Sep 2003, by Michael Rundell et al. The interface also includes a 'VIEW: List' and 'SORT BY: Date' dropdown menu.

- Based on *Event Registry*
- Full text wikification
- LexVoc terms
- Author locations
- Sources (conferences, etc.)
- Faceted searches
- Links to LexBib Zotero

- Info: <https://elex.is/tools-and-services/elexifinder/>
- Access: <https://finder.elex.is>

Elexifinder version 2: contents

Collections

- Conference proceedings
 - 2,018 items: eLex, Euralex, Globalex
- Journals
 - 4,145 items: 9 journals, complete
- Collective vols. and handbooks
 - 319 items: 12 volumes, complete
- Videos
 - 86 items

Top 10 publication languages

- English: 4,853
- German: 910
- Danish: 436
- Spanish: 395
- Swedish: 369
- French: 227
- Bokmål: 179
- Afrikaans: 135
- Slovene: 81
- Italian: 44
- (others: 83 items in 10 languages)

Outlook: Future plans

- Elexifinder / LexBib as a long-term service to the community
 - Elexifinder: <https://finder.elex.is>
 - LexBib: <https://lexbib.elex.is>
- Zotero-to-Wikibase bibliodata workflow
 - Reproducible for other domains
 - Zotero-Wikibase synchronization as python app

